

Electronic Supplementary Material

Title: Landscape management can foster pollinator richness in fragmented high-value habitats

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Supplementary datasets and R code

1. Biegerl_R_code_ProceedingsB.Rmd
2. Landscape_data.csv
3. DAG_data.csv

Available at the Dryad Digital Repository (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.dncjxm90>).

Supplementary Methods S1

DAG construction and validation

Directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) provides a rigorous framework for causal inference, enabling researchers to estimate causal effects from observational data using domain knowledge and accounting for confounding factors [1]. We constructed the DAG presented in the main text to express our understanding of the causal structure of our study system (Figure 2). To ensure the appropriateness of the DAG, DAG construction and validation followed Arif and MacNeil (2023) [1] and Ankan et al. (2021) [2]:

The most proximate causes of wild pollinator richness and abundance in a given grassland patch are processes of colonization, population growth, population decline, and extinction (hereafter “population dynamics”). None of these processes could be observed directly in our study design, but it is reasonable to expect them to be regulated by measurable conditions at local, landscape, and regional scales. At the local scale, we expect population dynamics to depend on floral resources, nesting resources, and the size of the habitat patch. At the landscape scale — operationally defined by a 2 km radius around each focal grassland patch — population dynamics could be influence by habitat connectivity (represented by the proportional cover of grassland in the landscape), agricultural practices (mean field size, annual crop cover, and organic farming), and conservation amenities (represented by the proportional cover of flowering fields). Finally, population dynamics are likely influenced by regional processes and conditions such as climate conditions (represented by mean annual temperature), geology, topography, biogeography, land use history, and social conditions driving (or constraining) human land management decisions. While beyond the scope of our study, we note these (largely unmeasured or unmeasurable) regional drivers explicitly because they have the potential to confound causal inferences made concerning lower-level drivers.

Additionally, although relationships between variables are represented as accurately as possible, some relationships or variables may still remain unobserved. For example, habitat area may still be correlated with landscape level variables when region is controlled for, e.g. through links to unmeasured latent variables. Furthermore, landscape-level variation in agricultural conditions (within regions) may act as a common cause, again indicating an omitted latent variable. We therefore

included a latent variable in the DAG to represent these possible unobserved relationships between landscape and local level variables.

Importantly, the local variables of calcareous grassland area, floral resources, and nesting resources can be expected to mediate in part the effects of landscape variables, insofar as the local variables are both causes of the response variables and caused by the landscape variables. For the same reason, the landscape variables — which also exert direct influence on the response variables — can function as confounds of the local variables. This calls for two parallel modeling procedures.

First, to obtain unbiased estimates of the causal effect of the local variables, it is necessary to condition the model on the confounding landscape variables. This yields unbiased estimates for the local variables but simultaneously biases the estimates for the landscape variables by conditioning on their mediators (i.e. the local variables). To obtain unbiased causal estimates for the landscape variables, it is necessary to fit a second model without the mediating local variables, thereby capturing the full causal effect of the landscape variables. In both models, we included region and mean annual temperature as fixed effects to mitigate potential confounds arising above the landscape level.

Figure S1. DAG constructed on dagitty.net to test for DAG consistency. Green circles represent exposure variables, blue circles represent outcome variables, and grey circles represent unobserved latent variables. Green arrows represent causal paths that are not biased, and grey arrows represent potential but unknown/unmeasured causal relationships.

After selecting variables and creating the DAG based on domain knowledge, it is necessary to check for DAG consistency. This means that the DAG, which declares multiple independencies, should hold against observational data. Therefore, we used the R package DAGitty [3], which provides a straightforward procedure to test whether a DAG is consistent with a data set. First, we added our DAG to the web interface at dagitty.net and exported the model to R Studio. In Figure S1, we can see that our DAG does not contain any open biasing paths and therefore, no adjustments are needed to estimate the total effect of our variables. The second step was to test which conditional independencies exist in the DAG and whether these independencies are consistent with the observational data. This was done with the localTests function of the DAGitty package. This function outputs the Pearson correlation coefficient, the 95% confidence interval and the p-value for each of the implied conditional independencies. We only observed low correlation coefficients (all p-values >0.05) which indicate that the conditional independence holds in the data. The results shown in Figure S2 indicate that there is no strong evidence against conditional independence for the tested relationships and that our DAG is consistent with the data.

Figure S2. For each implied conditional independence (y-axis) the Pearson correlation coefficient and the 95% confidence interval of the correlation coefficient (x-axis) is shown. All confidence intervals include the value 0, indicating non-significant results ($p > 0.05$), which means that conditional independencies hold in the observational data (Flwr = Flower resources, MAT = Mean annual temperature, Regn = Region, Flwf = Flowering fields, Hbtc = Habitat connectivity, Nestr = Nesting resources, Mnfs = Mean field size, Orgf = Organic farming, Ancc = Annual crop cover, Clga = Calcareous grassland area).

To further ensure the appropriateness of the DAG, we tested the variables in our DAG for residual spatial autocorrelation. We tested the similarity between nearby observations with DHARMA Morans I test for distance-based autocorrelation with the R package “DHARMA” [4] (function `testSpatialAutocorrelation`). We could not identify any issues meaning that nearby observations are not correlated ($p > 0.05$). Lastly, we checked for multicollinearity among the independent variables in our multiple regression model. Here we used a common measure of the amount of multicollinearity: the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and the function `vif()` provided by the R package “car” [5]. Values of VIF between predictor variables were under 5 indicating moderate correlations, which is not yet problematic and can be disregarded [6]. Only the variable “region” has high VIF values (> 5), but since region act as a control variable in our model and our variables of interest do not have high VIFs, the high VIF for region can be ignored. The complete and detailed workflow of DAG construction and validation, residual spatial autocorrelation and multicollinearity test in R Studio is provided in the supplementary material.

Despite the advantages of Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), it is important to mention possible limitations of the approach. The DAG builds on assumptions based on domain knowledge, literature and the experience of researchers to explain the studied system. The DAG can therefore help to understand complex ecological processes, but there is no guarantee that all assumptions are correct [1]. Since it is almost impossible to capture all the relations and interactions between variables that influence each other and since some variables cannot be identified or measured, DAGs are limited in their ability to represent an ecological system, and results should be interpreted with care. However, the approach allows readers to notice potential shortcomings or knowledge gaps within the DAG [1]. In addition, DAGs are non-parametric and do not replace the need for appropriate statistical model fitting and validation [7]. It is therefore important to stress test the DAG as much as possible and test for data consistency and independencies.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S3. Boxplots showing wild pollinator species richness and abundance data among study sites. Means, standard errors (SE) and outliers are given.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Results of generalized linear models. Model 1 (results in yellow) included following variables: Calcareous grassland area (hereafter habitat area), habitat connectivity, mean field size, organic farming and flowering field. Control variables were annual crop cover, region and mean annual temperature (estimates not shown). In model 2 (results in blue), the variables flower richness, flower cover and nesting sites (only in models for solitary bees) were added to model 1 with the variables of model 1 acting as control variables (estimates not shown). Estimates and 95% confidence interval are given. Bold estimates and intervals indicate significant effects (confidence intervals that do not include 1.0). Parameter estimates have been back-transformed from log-link-scale to the response scale that is why the estimates change around 1 and not 0. Some estimates and confidence intervals appear symmetrical even though they have been back transformed from the log link scale, but this is due to the number of decimal places displayed. More decimal places show the actual asymmetry of the intervals.

Predictor	Solitary bee species richness		Solitary bee abundance	
	estimate	Confidence interval	estimate	Confidence interval
Flower richness	1.007	[1.000, 1.013]	0.996	[0.985, 1.007]
Flower cover	1.382	[0.521, 3.585]	1.583	[0.354, 7.347]
Nesting sites	1.036	[1.007, 1.065]	1.060	[1.015, 1.109]
Habitat area	1.126	[1.032, 1.228]	1.223	[1.058, 1.414]
Habitat connectivity	1.023	[0.974, 1.073]	1.013	[0.935, 1.099]
Mean field size	0.914	[0.780, 1.070]	0.696	[0.531, 0.911]
Organic farming	0.999	[0.996, 1.002]	0.997	[0.992, 1.003]
Flowering fields	0.999	[0.978, 1.019]	0.996	[0.963, 1.030]

Predictor	Endangered solitary bee species richness		Endangered solitary bee abundance	
	estimate	Confidence interval	estimate	Confidence interval
Flower richness	1.007	[0.992, 1.021]	1.002	[0.982, 1.024]
Flower cover	0.513	[0.049, 4.722]	3.709	[0.196, 75.825]
Nesting sites	1.046	[0.983, 1.111]	1.063	[0.976, 1.161]
Habitat area	1.280	[1.053, 1.557]	1.461	[1.111, 1.922]
Habitat connectivity	1.015	[0.913, 1.128]	0.980	[0.847, 1.135]
Mean field size	0.796	[0.555, 1.137]	0.713	[0.435, 1.168]
Organic farming	0.998	[0.991, 1.005]	0.999	[0.989, 1.009]
Flowering fields	0.973	[0.928, 1.019]	0.987	[0.929, 1.050]

Predictor	Bumblebee species richness		Bumblebee abundance	
	estimate	Confidence interval	estimate	Confidence interval
Flower richness	1.008	[0.993, 1.023]	1.009	[0.988, 1.031]
Flower cover	2.212	[0.253, 17.276]	7.676	[0.534, 132.382]
Habitat area	1.005	[0.824, 1.226]	0.890	[0.668, 1.183]
Habitat connectivity	1.053	[0.942, 1.175]	0.860	[0.734, 1.009]
Mean field size	0.941	[0.653, 1.352]	1.126	[0.670, 1.897]
Organic farming	1.001	[0.994, 1.008]	1.011	[1.001, 1.021]
Flowering fields	1.007	[0.960, 1.054]	1.005	[0.940, 1.077]

Predictor	Hoverfly species richness		Hoverfly abundance	
	estimate	Confidence interval	estimate	Confidence interval
Flower richness	1.028	[1.013, 1.044]	1.029	[1.004, 1.055]
Flower cover	1.417	[0.200, 9.069]	2.964	[0.101, 116.300]
Habitat area	0.924	[0.763, 1.118]	1.046	[0.753, 1.453]

Habitat connectivity	1.027	[0.922, 1.142]	0.872	[0.724, 1.053]
Mean field size	1.255	[0.883, 1.784]	1.636	[0.880, 3.040]
Organic farming	0.997	[0.989, 1.005]	0.998	[0.986, 1.012]
Flowering fields	1.029	[0.985, 1.074]	1.058	[0.978, 1.151]

	Butterfly species richness		Butterfly abundance	
Flower richness	1.004	[0.996, 1.013]	1.009	[0.994, 1.024]
Flower cover	0.942	[0.454, 1.942]	4.240	[1.216, 14.976]
Habitat area	1.179	[1.073, 1.295]	1.498	[1.265, 1.773]
Habitat connectivity	1.041	[0.989, 1.095]	1.066	[0.974, 1.168]
Mean field size	1.041	[0.876, 1.238]	0.875	[0.654, 1.172]
Organic farming	1.001	[0.997, 1.004]	1.001	[0.995, 1.008]
Flowering fields	1.012	[0.991, 1.034]	1.006	[0.972, 1.043]

	Endangered butterfly species richness		Endangered butterfly abundance	
Flower richness	1.006	[0.984, 1.029]	1.002	[0.970, 1.034]
Flower cover	1.182	[0.195, 6.881]	6.256	[0.376, 112.598]
Habitat area	1.525	[1.194, 1.956]	1.741	[1.185, 2.569]
Habitat connectivity	1.152	[1.018, 1.303]	1.128	[0.911, 1.406]
Mean field size	1.187	[0.747, 1.887]	1.292	[0.682, 2.441]
Organic farming	1.006	[0.997, 1.014]	1.020	[1.006, 1.034]
Flowering fields	1.030	[0.971, 1.091]	0.992	[0.921, 1.073]

	Flower richness		Flower cover	
Habitat area	1.114	[1.044, 1.189]	1.055	[1.020, 1.092]
Habitat connectivity	1.043	[1.007, 1.081]	0.998	[0.980, 1.017]
Mean field size	1.109	[0.984, 1.250]	1.005	[0.946, 1.069]
Organic farming	1.002	[0.999, 1.004]	1.001	[0.999, 1.002]
Flowering fields	1.023	[1.008, 1.038]	1.003	[0.995, 1.010]

Supplementary Figures

Figure S4. Relationship between (endangered) solitary bee, bumblebee, (endangered) butterfly, hoverfly species richness and abundance and local variables: Calcareous grassland area (hereafter habitat area) (\log_{10} transformed), flower richness, flower cover, nesting sites and landscape variables: habitat connectivity, mean field size, organic farming, and flowering fields. Significant results of GLMs ($p < 0.05$) are shown in black, non-significant results are shown in grey regression lines.

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